

Mitosis Detection using YOLOv5 and EfficientNet

Engin Bozaba¹, Sercan Çayır¹, Eren Tekin¹, Süha Berk Kukuk¹, and Ahmed Imam Shah¹

¹Artificial Intelligence Research Team, ViraSoft Inc., Istanbul, Turkey

To accurately assess the prognosis of various tumors, mitosis detection plays a crucial role. The objective of the MIDOG 2022 MICCAI challenge is to develop approaches that are independent of tissue-related domain shifts and tissue types. We propose a two-stage mitosis detection system, utilizing YOLOv5 as the candidate mitosis generator and EfficientNet-B3 as the classification stage. The inclusion of the classification stage is aimed at reducing False Positives (FP). Our proposed method achieved a 0.60 F1-score and 0.71 precision on the MIDOG 2022 preliminary test data.

Mitosis Detection | YOLOv5 | EfficientNet

Correspondence: engin.bozaba@virasoft.com.tr

Introduction

The most typical kind of cancer in women is breast cancer, which is the second most frequent disease globally. The histological grade is a strong predictive factor for predicting the breast cancer's aggressiveness (1). The Nottingham Grading System aids in predicting the histological grade by evaluating three major tumor features which are mitotic rate, nuclear pleomorphism, and tubule formation (2). Nottingham Grading System claims that The prognostic value of the mitotic rate is the highest of all three features. In clinical practice, it takes a lot of time to determine and count mitosis, even in one high-power field (HPF). And also, differences in perceptions and experiences among clinicians may lead to different biased results. As a result, a reliable, automated approach for detecting and counting mitosis is needed.

Recently, many deep learning-based methods (3–5) have been used to detect mitotic objects. Despite being quite successful, a performance decline is frequently seen when the model is evaluated on data from some other datasets obtained by different scanners, laboratories, and sample preparations. It is seen that the difference in the training and test dataset emphasizes the effect on the model and the difficulty of the problem.

We provide a creative, effective deep learning-based approach to address the relevant issue. Inspired by Çayır et al (4), this study proposes a method to solve the problem in two stages. Çayır et al (4) first performed nuclei detection and then nuclei classification for mitosis. Instead of detecting nuclei in the first step, we performed candidate mitosis detection. Then the classification model was used to achieve high precision of our approach.

Methodology

The proposed method can be divided into two deep learning architectures, called YOLOv5-1 and EfficientNet-B3, respectively, to suggest candidate mitosis cells and identify the mitosis in a HPF.

YOLOv5. : YOLOv5 is single stage object detection method developed by Jocher et al (6). YOLOv5 consists of CSPDarknet53 as backbone feature extractor, Path Aggregation Network (PANet) as neck, YOLO layer as head. CSPDarknet53 allows more gradient flow over the network with DarkNet-53 and CSPNet strategy. Path aggregation network (PANet) is used to increase information flow with bottom ups and top down layers. And YOLOv5 compound scaling without image scaling is used for model scaling. Due to its speed and performance, this study uses the YOLOv5-1 model.

EfficientNet.

EfficientNet (7) which has compound coefficient for scaling all dimensions of depth/width/resolution is a convolutional neural network. In contrast to customary practice, which arbitrarily weights various components, these components are scaled uniformly by the scaling method using a set of fixed scaling coefficients. EfficientNet models scale from the EfficientNet-B0 baseline using a specific compound coefficient. The EfficientNet-B3 model is used to classify candidate mitosis.

Experiment

Dataset. The dataset used in the study was obtained from MIDOG 2022 (8). The training dataset contains 354 annotated regions of interest (ROI). In total, ROIs consist of 11051 non-mitotic figures and 9501 mitotic figures. Using sliding window, 512x512 tiles were cropped from cases. Thus, our models can be trained. Each candidate mitosis detected by YOLOv5 was cropped for classification stage. Every cropped object was resized to 224x224 when entering the classification model. Detailed list of training cases:

- 44 Canine Lung Cancer cases scanned with 3DHitech Panoramic Scan II
- 150 Human Breast Cancer cases scanned using three scanners, part of MIDOG2021(9) dataset
- 55 Canine Lymphoma cases scanned with 3DHitech Panoramic Scan II

- 55 Human neuroendocrine tumor cases scanned with Hamamatsu NanoZoomer XR
- 50 Canine Cutaneous Mast Cell Tumor cases scanned with Aperio ScanScope CS2

Experiment Setup. While training, both models were optimized separately. To train YOLOV5-1, all annotated 512x512 tiles including mitosis were split in a ratio of 85:15 for training and validation respectively. Vertical flip, horizontal flip, scaling, mosaic, and HSV data augmentation methods were applied to the training data set. All annotated mitosis tiles were resized to 512 pixels x 512 pixels. The mitosis detection model was finetuned with a batch size of 32, an initial learning rate of 0.01, Stochastic Gradient Descent as an optimizer, and an optimizer weight decay of 5.0E-4. And also A YoloV5-1 architecture, which was pre-trained on the COCO dataset was fine-tuned for mitosis detection. In the EfficientNet-B3, the parameter values such as initial learning rate, batch size epoch, and image size are set to 0.001, 10, 32, and 224x224 respectively. The ADAM algorithm is used as an optimizer to obtain the optimized model. At the start of the training, the weights of the model are initialized from the IMAGENET. These models are trained and tested on a computer with an Intel i9-8950HK CPU, an NVIDIA GTX 3090 GPU, and 16 GB RAM.

Results. The models were evaluated using the mAP@50 and F1-score metrics. On the validation data, YOLOv5 achieved a score of 0.60 with mAP@50, while EfficientNet-B3 attained an accuracy of 0.85. Furthermore, the proposed method achieved a 0.60 F1-score and 0.71 precision on the preliminary test data for MIDOG 2022(8).

Discussion and Conclusion

The primary aim of this study was to automate the individual identification of mitosis in histopathology images. To achieve this goal, we employed YOLOv5 and EfficientNet for mitosis detection. We notably improved precision scores by implementing data augmentation techniques on the dataset and incorporating a classification component. It is worth noting that our results were achieved without stain normalization. In future research, further advancements can be made by expanding the dataset, enabling enhanced training and error analysis. This approach holds the potential for even more successful outcomes.

Bibliography

1. Balamurali Murugesan, Sakthivel Selvaraj, Kaushik Sarveswaran, Keerthi Ram, Jayaraj Joseph, and Mohanasankar Sivaprakasam. Deep detection and classification of mitotic figures. In *Medical Imaging 2019: Digital Pathology*, volume 10956, pages 177–182. SPIE, 2019.
2. Maschenka CA Balkenhol, David Tellez, Willem Vreuls, Pieter C Clahsen, Hans Pinckaers, Francesco Ciompi, Peter Bult, and Jeroen AWM van der Laak. Deep learning assisted mitotic counting for breast cancer. *Laboratory investigation*, 99(11):1596–1606, 2019.
3. Tahir Mahmood, Muhammad Arsalan, Muhammad Owais, Min Beom Lee, and Kang Ryoung Park. Artificial intelligence-based mitosis detection in breast cancer histopathology images using faster r-cnn and deep cnns. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 9(3):749, 2020.
4. Sercan Çayır, Gizem Solmaz, Huseyin Kusetogullari, Fatma Tokat, Engin Bozaba, Sencer Karakaya, Leonardo Obinna Iherne, Eren Tekin, Gülşah Özsoy, Samet Ayaltı, et al. Mitnet: a novel dataset and a two-stage deep learning approach for mitosis recognition in whole slide images of breast cancer tissue. *Neural Computing and Applications*, pages 1–15, 2022.

5. Anabia Sohail, Asifullah Khan, Noorul Wahab, Aneela Zameer, and Saranjam Khan. A multi-phase deep cnn based mitosis detection framework for breast cancer histopathological images. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1):1–18, 2021.
6. Glenn Jocher, Alex Stoken, Jirka Borovec, NanoCode012, ChristopherSTAN, Liu Changyu, Laughing, tkianai, Adam Hogan, lorenzomamma, yxNONG, AlexWang1900, Laurentiu Diaconu, Marc, wanghaoyang0106, ml5ah, Doug, Francisco Ingham, Frederik, Guilhen, Hatovix, Jake Poznanski, Jiacong Fang, Lijun Yu, changyu98, Mingyu Wang, Naman Gupta, Osama Akhtar, PetrDvoracek, and Prashant Rai. ultralytics/yolov5: v3.1 - Bug Fixes and Performance Improvements, October 2020.
7. Andrew G Howard, Menglong Zhu, Bo Chen, Dmitry Kalenichenko, Weijun Wang, Tobias Weyand, Marco Andreetto, and Hartwig Adam. Mobilenets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.04861*, 2017.
8. Marc Aubreville, Christof Bertram, Katharina Breining, Samir Jabari, Nikolas Stathonikos, and Mitko Veta. Mitosis domain generalization challenge 2022. In *25th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2022)*, 2022. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6362337.
9. Marc Aubreville, Nikolas Stathonikos, Christof A Bertram, Robert Kloplesch, Natalie ter Hoeve, Francesco Ciompi, Frauke Wilm, Christian Marzahl, Taryn A Donovan, Andreas Maier, et al. Mitosis domain generalization in histopathology images—the midog challenge. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2204.03742*, 2022.